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Research Article

MANAGEMENT IN RUSSIA: FEATURES AND DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

The article discusses current problems and features of management in Russia, identifies its main areas of development. The analysis of the importance of the principles of management and personal qualities necessary for the successful work of the modern manager. A model of an effective Russian manager of the 21st century has been proposed, and the competencies defined, the achievement of which will ensure the effectiveness of managers in modern Russia.

Keywords: *management, problems, features, development, digital economy, Russia.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Russia's transition to the path of building a new society, to a new type of relations, management, education and training of professional managers revealed the inconsistency of the old principles and methods of management. The real lack of knowledge and skills necessary for successful work manifests itself. Russian leaders are transferring Western experience into their reality, mechanically transforming it without in-depth analysis and reflection. At the same time, a positive result is impossible without taking into account the peculiarities of the Russian management, the Russian

mentality and the complex socio-psychological situation, which play a significant role in the formation of a modern management that is different from the Western one.

In identifying the features of Russian management, we considered the concept of "culture" as the basis of management. The figure 1 shows a model of the interdependence of cultures of different levels: the culture of the individual; team culture; culture of society. They all influence each other, the basis is the mentality, as part of the biological in man.

Figure 1: Mutual influence model the cultures of different levels

The underestimation of the moral climate and the fact that in the traditions of the Russian mentality lies a peculiar way of relating national values and harmony, as well as the idea of a sacred attitude to the state and its interests as the highest value and, as a result, the negative attitude to private property in the public consciousness Russians

The transition to market relations has led not only to a change in self-consciousness, but also the structures of organizations that have become less identical in structure. Much attention has been paid to small businesses. The hasty privatization has led to the fact that most of the shares of a number of powerful enterprises for nothing have been acquired by the directors, which do not have the skills to work in the market, in a competitive environment. All these peculiarities set before the Russian management tasks that require a quick solution - creating a system for training professionally trained managers who are able to search for new solutions, constantly raising the cultural level, expanding the horizon of knowledge and thinking, forming a certain creative and creative mentality, the driving part of intellectual capital.

In order to identify the distinctive characteristics of a modern manager, a sociological survey of managers of trade enterprises was conducted. As a result of the analysis, a natural interdependence of some personal qualities and principles of management was revealed: internal freedom and the principle of independence, orientation to the subordinate and the principle of the participation of all in the results (in management), flexibility and the principle of pluralism of opinions, etc.

A number of essential personal qualities of a modern manager were highlighted: inner freedom; ability to work in a group, to be its leader; high degree of sociability; flexibility; the desire for risk; tact in work; orientation to the subordinate who plays the main role in achieving the goal; desire to get accurate and reliable information.

Taking into account the strengths and weaknesses of Russian management makes it possible to build a matrix of the specifics of Russian management, analyze the problems of Russian management and

find ways to resolve them, taking into account the strengths of both common features and specific features. A study of enterprises of trade allowed us to identify significant problems of the management of enterprises of this type and outline the range of priority problems, including: the originality of the national and organizational cultures. Unformed organizational culture of Russian enterprises; low level of social responsibility and managerial ethics; providing enterprises with qualified managerial personnel (advanced training and retraining); systemic crisis of the economy; corruption and shadow economy.

One of the main problems of Russian management is - training (managers). Russia really needs professional managers, managers of a new type, and the effectiveness of management in modern conditions of the announced digitalization of the economy depends on it.

A modern professional manager, in our opinion, should possess the necessary set of knowledge, skills and abilities that can be divided into two systems: the system of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the learning process and the system of personal and business skills.

In Russia, personal relationships play a much more important role than in a typical Western organization. Such a situation could be considered quite normal at a stage when companies only formed and loyalty was more important than professionalism, but the nature of personal relationships with decision makers, rather than professionalism or leadership skills, remains in many companies the most important factor in career advancement. . In many Russian organizations, there is in fact an alternative hierarchy that is built on personal connections and often contradicts the organization's professional requirements, which creates certain problems.

In Russia, with a formally high level of education, there is an urgent problem of lack of social and behavioral skills (for example, the ability to work with people), as well as high-order cognitive skills ("ability to solve problems, the ability to make non-standard decisions).

For decades, the Soviet management system was kept on a strict hierarchy, and therefore many Russian business leaders, despite their individual merits, do not know how to work in a team and build a team approach in the organization as a whole. At the same time, Western companies are increasingly aware of

the importance of creating a command environment in which all managers work together and on an equal footing, making their own special contribution to the overall success of the company. Teamwork and horizontal interaction are equally important in all organizations, both in legal and consulting firms, and in production companies - especially those that require expertise from a wide range of specialists. For example, the management of an oil field involves managing the reservoir, well stock, and ground infrastructure, and one professional, even of the highest class, cannot always make a qualified decision; therefore, there are cross-functional teams in Western oil companies that manage the field. In Russia, this practice takes root slowly.

It is necessary to begin the process of introducing a team approach to the management of domestic organizations from a higher education level. To this end, in the educational university developed in 2014, the Financial University, as a result of mastering the educational program in the direction of training, "Management" formed the following competence of the graduate: "readiness for individual and teamwork, compliance with ethical standards in interpersonal professional communication (SLK-2). Implementing this competence is helped by the introduction of this standard into the structure of the educational program in the "Management" direction, such an element as "research work", with the goal of creating universal and professional competencies that ensure the implementation of creative projects of students of interdisciplinary research projects, term papers, final qualifying work.

Thus, the manager should have deep knowledge and a wide range of professional skills, the leading role in helping to resolve the problem that has arisen is given to the Russian education system.

Considering the high demands of the digital economy on the skills and competencies of the workforce, more attention is required both to systems of additional education and retraining, to create a society where people will consciously relate to their own skills, perceive self-education as a natural part of success in the labor market, because knowledge and information key resources of the information age. In modern conditions, the main tool for creating value added and the key mechanism for managing all technological processes are data and software products, they are moving to digital clouds, and the Internet becomes the main channel and data circulation space, the requirements for management processes in the 21st century are changing

dramatically.

The transition to a digital economy means an increase in observability, speed, accuracy, flexibility, and due to this, the controllability of all production and technological processes, and their achievement of high levels of complexity.

Analysis of the research results revealed the following features of Russian management: the dominance of personal relationships over professional ones; inability to work in a team; excessive control and unclear assignment of duties; lack of experience and culture of staff development; traditions of a partocratic approach to management; mentality: ideas of conciliarity, negative attitude towards private property; the existence of a special discipline of labor based on community, mutual aid.

CONCLUSION:

Having considered the most important problems and peculiarities of Russian management, we derived a model of an effective Russian manager of the 21st century, from which it follows that the digital economy is a serious challenge for Russian management and, in time, to “jump into the last car of the outgoing train” of the new industrial revolution, in our opinion, the 21st century manager should have the following competencies: multilingual; understanding of interdisciplinary communication; ability to work in conditions of high uncertainty; creative and behavioral skills; ability to work both with teams and with individuals; high order cognitive skills; perspective vision; self-reliance; turning circumstances into opportunities; action orientation; concentration on the essentials.

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